

L-isoleucine-Schiff base copper(II) coordination polymer: Crystal Structure, Spectroscopic, Hirshfeld Surface, and DFT Analyses

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Figure S1. (a) Intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions in L-HCl-IleCu, (b) viewing the same short contacts in Hirshfeld surface mapped with dnorm.

Figure S2. Infrared spectra of the ligand L-HCl-Ile and complex CuLCl.

Figure S3. Thermogravimetric (TG/DTG) curves of complex CuLCl.

Figure S4. UV-Vis spectra of ligand and complex CuLCl.

Figure S5. EPR spectra of complex CuLCl in polycrystalline at room temperature.

Figure S6. EPR spectra of complex CuLCl in solution state at 77 K.

Figure S7. Comparison between experimental and calculated UV-vis spectra

Figure S8. Experimental (top) and calculated with UM06-2X/LANL2DZ method (bottom) IR spectra.

Table S1. Electronic transitions, their wavelength major contributions and their percentage calculated by TD-DFT M06-2X/LANL2DZ.

No.	Wavelength h (nm)	Osc. Strengt h	Major contribution
1	1434.84	0	H-32(B)->LUMO(B) (29%), H-3(B)->LUMO(B) (11%), HOMO(B)->LUMO(B) (21%)
2	1068.37	0.0017	H-34(B)->LUMO(B) (10%), H-33(B)->LUMO(B) (12%), H-31(B)->LUMO(B) (18%)
3	761.01	0.0003	H-26(B)->LUMO(B) (53%)
4	730.09	0.0001	H-30(B)->LUMO(B) (10%), H-29(B)->LUMO(B) (56%)
5	472.46	0.0002	H-32(B)->LUMO(B) (11%), HOMO(B)->LUMO(B) (69%)
6	426.66	0	HOMO(A)->LUMO(A) (45%), HOMO(B)->L+1(B) (43%)
7	345.24	0.0226	H-4(B)->LUMO(B) (50%), H-1(B)->LUMO(B) (17%)
8	336.46	0.0166	HOMO(A)->LUMO(A) (13%), H-1(B)->LUMO(B) (53%), HOMO(B)->L+1(B) (16%)
9	333.83	0	H-2(A)->LUMO(A) (23%), H-2(B)->L+1(B) (21%)
10	319.57	0.0038	H-3(B)->LUMO(B) (45%), H-2(B)->LUMO(B) (30%)
11	310.27	0.186	HOMO(A)->LUMO(A) (22%), H-4(B)->LUMO(B) (32%), H-1(B)->LUMO(B) (16%), HOMO(B)->L+1(B) (22%)
12	290.50	0.0075	H-3(B)->LUMO(B) (21%), H-2(B)->LUMO(B) (52%)
13	289.77	0.0004	HOMO(A)->L+2(A) (15%), HOMO(A)->L+3(A) (15%), HOMO(B)->L+3(B) (11%), HOMO(B)->L+4(B) (17%)
14	277.13	0.0001	H-4(A)->LUMO(A) (48%), H-3(A)->LUMO(A) (18%)
15	274.82	0.0052	H-10(B)->LUMO(B) (68%)
16	266.71	0.0011	H-1(A)->L+7(A) (35%), H-1(B)->L+8(B) (28%)
17	249.75	0.0053	H-3(A)->L+7(A) (24%), H-3(B)->L+8(B) (31%)
18	248.35	0.049	H-11(B)->LUMO(B) (18%), H-2(B)->L+1(B) (13%)
19	245.03	0.0302	H-2(A)->LUMO(A) (13%), H-1(B)->L+1(B) (11%)
20	243.79	0.0066	H-1(A)->L+7(A) (30%), H-1(B)->L+8(B) (35%)
21	232.17	0.0111	HOMO(A)->L+1(A) (80%)
22	231.58	0.1805	H-1(A)->LUMO(A) (22%), H-11(B)->LUMO(B) (10%), H-4(B)->L+1(B) (12%), H-1(B)->L+1(B) (22%)
23	229.78	0.0599	H-4(B)->L+1(B) (43%), H-2(B)->L+1(B) (12%)
24	225.92	0.0085	H-2(A)->LUMO(A) (10%), H-1(A)->LUMO(A) (20%), H-1(B)->L+1(B) (21%)
25	223.86	0.039	H-2(A)->LUMO(A) (18%), H-1(A)->LUMO(A) (13%), H-2(B)->L+1(B) (22%), H-1(B)->L+1(B) (17%)
26	220.33	0.0014	HOMO(B)->L+2(B) (25%)
27	220.21	0.0008	H-5(B)->LUMO(B) (39%)
28	219.1269	0.0052	H-11(B)->LUMO(B) (15%), H-7(B)->LUMO(B) (23%)
29	216.2716	0.001	H-5(B)->LUMO(B) (18%), HOMO(B)->L+2(B) (16%), HOMO(B)->L+3(B) (14%), HOMO(B)->L+9(B) (10%)
30	213.9835	0.0004	HOMO(A)->L+8(A) (31%), HOMO(B)->L+9(B) (30%)
31	209.6169	0.0191	H-11(B)->L+1(B) (31%)
32	209.1572	0.333	HOMO(A)->L+2(A) (10%), HOMO(B)->L+4(B) (19%)
33	208.3978	0.151	H-2(A)->L+2(A) (11%), HOMO(A)->L+3(A) (11%)
34	205.3364	0.0463	H-3(B)->L+1(B) (38%)
35	203.9046	0.0066	H-4(A)->LUMO(A) (10%), H-3(A)->LUMO(A) (24%), H-3(B)->L+1(B) (17%)
36	202.7476	0.1272	H-3(A)->LUMO(A) (18%), HOMO(A)->L+2(A) (11%), H-3(B)->L+1(B) (13%)
37	200.3979	0.0072	H-5(A)->LUMO(A) (23%), H-11(B)->L+1(B) (10%)
38	199.8359	0	H-6(A)->LUMO(A) (22%), H-5(B)->L+1(B) (15%)
39	198.9253	0.0006	H-9(B)->LUMO(B) (54%), H-7(B)->LUMO(B) (27%)
40	198.594	0.0013	HOMO(A)->L+8(A) (42%), HOMO(B)->L+9(B) (40%)

Table S2. Experimental IR, and the theoretical frequencies (ω , cm^{-1}), infrared intensities (I_{IR} , km mol^{-1}), for the ---- complex, in the range 3900–1080 cm^{-1}

No.	ω_{exp}	ω	ω_{scaled}	I_{IR}	Vibrational mode	No.	ω_{exp}	ω	ω_{scaled}	I_{IR}	Vibrational mode
1		3269.21	3099.21	0.969 4	$\nu\text{C-H}_s$ (C6-H2, C7-H3, C9-H4)	27	1395	150 9.58	1431.09	132.5 20	$\delta_{\text{sc}}\text{C-H}$ (C14-[H14, H16], C13-[H11, H13], C11-[H8, H9], C10-[H5, H7]), $\rho_{\text{w}}\text{C-H}$ (C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3)
2		3266.47	3096.62	1.022	$\nu\text{C-H}_a$ (C6-H2, C7-H3, C9-H4)	28		150 2.79	1424.65	5.118	$\delta_{\text{sc}}\text{C-H}$ (C14-[H14, H16], C13-[H11, H13], C11-[H8, H9], C10-[H5, H7])
3		3248.38	3079.46	0.238 3	$\nu\text{C-H}_a$ (C6-H2, C7-H3)	29	1357	146 2.94	1386.87	118.6 15	$\delta_{\text{sc}}\text{C-H}$ (C14-[H14, H16], C13-[H11, H13], C11-[H8, H9], C10-[H5, H7]), $\rho_{\text{r}}\text{C-C}_s$ (C9-[C8,C4], C6-[C5,C7]) $\rho_{\text{w}}\text{C-H}$ (C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3)
4		3227.59	3059.76	11.73 91	$\nu\text{C-H}_s$ (C10-[H5, H6, H7])						
5	2996	3168.94	3004.15	22.66 12	$\nu\text{C-H}_a$ (C14-[H14, H15, H16])	30	1329	144 9.91	1374.52	24.81 7	$\delta_{\text{sc}}\text{C-H}_s$ (C10-[H5, H6, H7], C13-[H11, H12, H13])
6		3166.83	3002.16	2.279 6	$\nu\text{C-H}_a$ (C10-[H6, H7])	31		144 9.25	1373.88	6.058	$\delta_{\text{sc}}\text{C-H}_s$ (C10-[H5, H6, H7], C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
7		3162.12	2997.76	46.53 37	$\nu\text{C-H}$ (C13-H12) _a (C13-[H11, H13]) _s	32		143 2.34	1357.86	23.41 5	$\delta_{\text{sc}}\text{C-H}_s$ (C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
8	2967	3142.68	2979.26	59.45 59	$\nu\text{C-H}_a$ (C14-[H15, H16], C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C13-H11, H13)	33		141 7.49 5	1343.78	3.904 5	$\rho_{\text{w}}\text{C-H}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
9		3137.00	2973.87	10.18 78	$\nu\text{C-H}$ (C2-H1, C14-H15)	34	1305	140 7.37	1334.19	10.56 6	$\rho_{\text{r}}\text{C-C}_a$ (C9-[C8,C4], C6-[C5,C7]), $\rho_{\text{w}}\text{C-H}$ (C2-H1, C10-[H5, H6, H7], C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
10		3133.01	2970.09	19.97 33	$\nu\text{C-H}_a$ (C14-[H15, H16], C2-H1, C13-[H11, H13])	35		138 9.36	1317.12	0.147	$\rho_{\text{w}}\text{C-H}$ (C11-[H9], C12-H10)
11	2950	3111.85	2950.03	4.701 4	$\nu\text{C-H}$ (C2-H1, C12-H10, C14-[H14, H15, H16]) _s (C11-[H8, H9], C13-[H13, H11]) _a	36		137 0.97	1299.68	22.24 6	$\rho_{\text{w}}\text{C-H}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3)

12	2937	3092.51	2931.701	8.3972	ν C-H _a (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10)	37	1288	135	1284.62	144.4	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3)
13		3088.83	2928.21	2.7077	ν C-H _s (C10-[H5, H6, H7])	38		134	1270.82	31.82	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3)
14	2896	3052.95	2894.193	32.9946	ν C-H _s (C13-[H11, H12, H13])	39	1257	132	1256.61	69.48	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C9-H4, C6-H2)
15	2879	3041.42	2883.263	24.5283	ν C-H _s (C14-[H14, H15, H16], C11-[H8, H9])	40		131	1245.20	3.857	ν C4-C9, $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C9-H4, C6-H2)
16		3040.31	2882.211	21.081	ν C-H _s (C14-[H14, H15, H16], C11-[H8, H9])	41	1235	128	1218.79	171.9	ν C1-O1, $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C9-H4, C6-H2)
17	1612	1735.28	1645.042	602.4329	ν C1=O2	42	1209	127	1211.14	89.16	$\delta_{\text{scC-C}}$ (C4-[C3, C5]), $\rho_{\text{rC-Ca}}$ (C9-[C4, C8]), $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C6-H2, C7-H3, C9-H4, C2-H1)
18	1583	1697.22	1608.968	276.0373	(ν C3-N, ν C5-O3, ν C4-C9, ν C6-C7) _s , $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C6-H2, C7-H3, C9-H4, C10-[H5, H7])	43	1187	125	1185.71	35.39	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
19		1690.70	1602.781	56.6501	(ν C3-N, ν C8-C9, ν C5-C6) _s , $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C6-H2, C7-H3, C9-H4, C10-[H5, H7])	44	1166	122	1162.14	22.07	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
20	1511	1604.41	1520.983	146.0515	(ν C3-N, ν C4-C5, ν C7-C8) _s , $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C6-H2, C7-H3, C9-H4, C10-[H5, H7])	45	1131	118	1127.39	9.646	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
21	1464	1552.60	1471.867	30.0428	$\delta_{\text{scC-H}}$ (C14-[H14, H15], C13-[H12, H13])	46		117	1117.14	2.657	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3, C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
22	1416	1536.20	1456.318	12.7389	$\delta_{\text{scC-H}}$ (C10-[H5, H7], C14-[H14, H15], C11-[H8, H9])	47		115	1093.01	13.54	$\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3, C10-[H5, H6, H7], C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
23		1532.32	1452.636	51.254	$\delta_{\text{scC-H}}$ (C10-[H6, H7]), $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C9-H4)	48	1092	114	1088.39	21.40	ν C8-Cl, $\rho_{\text{rC-Ca}}$ (C7-[C6, C8]), $\rho_{\text{wC-H}}$ (C2-H1, C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3, C10-[H5, H6, H7],)

24	1528.50	1449.02	6.1033	δ_{sc} C-H(C14-[H15, H16], C13-[H11, H12])	49	111	1056.78	12.39	ν C2-N, δ_{sc} C-C _s (C6-[C5, C7],C9-[C4, C8]), ρ_w C-H (C6-H2, C7-H3, C9-H4, C10-[H5, H6, H7])	
25	1524.88	1445.58	7.0945	δ_{sc} C-H(C14-[H15, H16], C13-[H12, H13])	50	1043	109	1040.83	23.61	ν C2-N, δ_{sc} C-C _s (C6-[C5, C7],C9-[C4, C8]), ρ_w C-H (C10-[H5, H6, H7])
26	1513.13	1434.45	8.326	δ_{sc} C-H(C14-[H15, H16], C13-[H11, H13], C11-[H8, H9], C10-[H5, H7]), ρ_w C-H (C9-H4, C6-H2, C7-H3)	51	108	1025.72	2.239	ρ_w C-H(C2-H1, C10-[H5, H6, H7], C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])	

*Abbreviations: ν , stretching; δ_{sc} , scissoring; ρ_w , wagging; ρ_r , rocking; γ out-of-plane bending. Subscripts: a, asymmetric; s, symmetric.

Table S3. Experimental IR, and the theoretical frequencies (ω , cm^{-1}), infrared intensities (IIR, km mol^{-1}), for the ---- complex, in the range 1080-480 cm^{-1}

No.	ω_{exp}	ω	ω_{scaled}	IIR	Vibrational mode
52	1017	1069.002	1013.414	2.2207	ρ_w C-H(C2-H1, C10-[H5, H6, H7], C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
53		1024.349	971.0825	0.6472	γ (C6-H2, C7-H3)
54	962	1008.699	956.247	1.9294	δ_{sc} C-C(C6-[C5, C7],C9-[C4, C8]), ν N-Cu, ρ_w C-H(C2-H1, C10-[H5, H6, H7], C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
55		996.7218	944.8923	1.3463	δ_{sc} C-C(C6-[C5, C7],C9-[C4, C8]), ν N-Cu, ρ_w C-H(C2-H1, C10-[H5, H6, H7], C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
56		989.4396	937.9887	2.4926	ρ_w C-H(C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
57	924	969.1427	918.7473	36.2884	δ_{sc} C2-C1-O1 _s , ρ_w C-H(C10-[H5, H6, H7], C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
58		956.6924	906.9444	3.1193	ρ_w C-H(C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
59	894	935.2307	886.5987	8.5329	γ C9-H4
60	869	906.3851	859.2531	7.6788	δ_{sc} C-C(C8-[C7, C9]), ν C3-C10, ν O3-Cu, ν C8-Cl
61	841	883.7278	837.774	60.6371	γ C-H(C6-H2, C7-H3)
62		870.6632	825.3887	59.5712	δ_{sc} C-O(C1-[O1,O2]), ν O1-Cu, ρ_w C-H(C11-[H8, H9], C12-H10, C13-[H11, H12, H13], C14-[H14, H15, H16])
63		854.3046	809.8808	7.351	ν C-C(C12-[C11, C13, C14])
64	772	827.9208	784.8689	109.4205	ν N-Cu, ν O3-Cu, δ_{sc} C-C(C4-[C3, C5])
65		778.8587	738.358	1.8069	γ C-H (C6-H2, C9-H4)
66		754.232	715.0119	7.0602	γ C1-[O1, O2]
67		733.3749	695.2394	5.9983	δ_{sc} C1-[O1, O2] _s
68	711	712.6085	675.5529	40.9686	(ν N-Cu, ν O3-Cu, ν O1-Cu) _a
69		697.7319	661.4498	0.0248	(ν N-Cu, ν O3-Cu, ν O1-Cu) _s
70		638.1498	604.966	0.4674	γ C3-C4, γ C7-H3, γ C3-N
71	649	630.3695	597.5903	18.7082	ρ_w C6-[C5, C7], ρ_w C5-O3

72	557	584.0815	553.7093	25.5506	q _w C4-[C5, C9], q _w C5-O3
73	537	545.3869	517.0268	20.9895	γC-C(C6-C5, C7-C8, C4-C3), γC3-N, γC5-O3
74		501.1339	475.0749	5.8158	γC-C(C6-C5, C7-C8, C4-C3), γC3-N
75		487.4654	462.1172	25.037	δ _{sc} C4-[C3, C5], q _r (O1-Cu-O3)

*Abbreviations: ν, stretching; δ_{sc}, scissoring; q_w, wagging; q_r, rocking; γ out-of-plane bending. Subscripts: a, asymmetric; s, symmetric

Table S4. Atomic coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for CuLcl. U(eq) is defined as one third of the trace of the orthogonalized U^{ij} tensor.

	x	y	z	U(eq)
C(1)	-85(5)	3211(3)	6959(2)	12(1)
C(2)	223(5)	3443(2)	6391(2)	13(1)
C(3)	915(5)	4232(2)	6222(2)	11(1)
C(4)	2122(5)	5566(2)	6437(2)	12(1)
C(5)	3171(5)	5869(2)	6945(2)	13(1)
C(6)	531(6)	6160(3)	6297(2)	17(1)
C(7)	1167(6)	6966(3)	6056(2)	21(1)
C(8)	-509(8)	7523(3)	6024(3)	47(2)
C(9)	2062(9)	6861(3)	5485(3)	46(2)
C(10)	1134(6)	4393(2)	5605(2)	14(1)
C(11)	-108(5)	2861(3)	5977(2)	13(1)
C(12)	-684(6)	2103(2)	6104(2)	13(1)
C(13)	-1003(6)	1862(2)	6651(2)	14(1)
C(14)	-696(6)	2414(2)	7066(2)	14(1)
C(15)	8141(5)	5490(3)	7997(2)	13(1)
C(16)	7015(5)	5751(2)	8501(2)	11(1)
C(17)	5800(6)	7072(2)	8745(2)	11(1)
C(18)	5130(5)	7873(2)	8596(2)	11(1)
C(19)	4845(5)	8128(3)	8036(2)	14(1)
C(20)	4260(6)	8936(2)	7948(2)	16(1)
C(21)	3936(6)	9465(3)	8372(2)	16(1)
C(22)	4190(6)	9195(2)	8915(2)	14(1)
C(23)	4760(5)	8430(3)	9025(2)	13(1)
C(24)	5983(6)	6879(2)	9359(2)	15(1)
C(25)	5411(5)	5141(3)	8592(2)	16(1)
C(26)	6016(6)	4300(3)	8765(2)	19(1)
C(27)	4311(8)	3745(3)	8769(2)	33(1)
C(28)	6962(8)	4315(3)	9335(2)	35(1)
Cl(1)	-1011(2)	1396(1)	5568(1)	18(1)
Cl(2)	3813(1)	9864(1)	9467(1)	19(1)
Cu(1)	5796(1)	6624(1)	7582(1)	12(1)
Cu(2)	824(1)	4746(1)	7373(1)	12(1)
N(1)	1324(4)	4776(2)	6586(1)	11(1)
N(2)	6233(4)	6549(2)	8370(1)	11(1)
O(1)	2592(4)	5646(2)	7417(1)	15(1)
O(2)	74(4)	3682(2)	7389(1)	16(1)
O(3)	4524(4)	6346(2)	6879(1)	15(1)
O(4)	7616(4)	5739(2)	7524(1)	14(1)
O(5)	9511(4)	5028(2)	8068(1)	14(1)
O(6)	5021(4)	7682(2)	7591(1)	15(1)

Table S5. Bond lengths [Å] and angles [°] for CuLCl.

C(1)-O(2)	1.308(5)
C(1)-C(14)	1.424(6)
C(1)-C(2)	1.440(6)
C(2)-C(11)	1.413(6)
C(2)-C(3)	1.465(6)
C(3)-N(1)	1.297(5)
C(3)-C(10)	1.521(5)
C(4)-N(1)	1.480(5)
C(4)-C(5)	1.525(6)
C(4)-C(6)	1.548(6)
C(4)-H(4)	1.0000
C(5)-O(3)	1.264(5)
C(5)-O(1)	1.269(5)
C(6)-C(7)	1.535(6)
C(6)-H(6A)	0.9900
C(6)-H(6B)	0.9900
C(7)-C(8)	1.520(7)
C(7)-C(9)	1.529(7)
C(7)-H(7)	1.0000
C(8)-H(8A)	0.9800
C(8)-H(8B)	0.9800
C(8)-H(8C)	0.9800
C(9)-H(9A)	0.9800
C(9)-H(9B)	0.9800
C(9)-H(9C)	0.9800
C(10)-H(10A)	0.9800
C(10)-H(10B)	0.9800
C(10)-H(10C)	0.9800
C(11)-C(12)	1.366(6)
C(11)-H(11)	0.9500
C(12)-C(13)	1.397(5)
C(12)-Cl(1)	1.767(4)
C(13)-C(14)	1.380(6)
C(13)-H(13)	0.9500
C(14)-H(14)	0.9500
C(15)-O(5)	1.259(5)
C(15)-O(4)	1.272(5)
C(15)-C(16)	1.524(5)
C(16)-N(2)	1.478(5)
C(16)-C(25)	1.550(5)
C(16)-H(16)	1.0000
C(17)-N(2)	1.295(5)
C(17)-C(18)	1.466(5)
C(17)-C(24)	1.521(5)
C(18)-C(23)	1.416(5)
C(18)-C(19)	1.432(6)
C(19)-O(6)	1.311(5)
C(19)-C(20)	1.429(6)
C(20)-C(21)	1.373(6)
C(20)-H(20)	0.9500
C(21)-C(22)	1.395(6)

C(21)-H(21)	0.9500
C(22)-C(23)	1.367(5)
C(22)-Cl(2)	1.759(4)
C(23)-H(23)	0.9500
C(24)-H(24A)	0.9800
C(24)-H(24B)	0.9800
C(24)-H(24C)	0.9800
C(25)-C(26)	1.528(6)
C(25)-H(25A)	0.9900
C(25)-H(25B)	0.9900
C(26)-C(27)	1.532(7)
C(26)-C(28)	1.534(6)
C(26)-H(26)	1.0000
C(27)-H(27A)	0.9800
C(27)-H(27B)	0.9800
C(27)-H(27C)	0.9800
C(28)-H(28A)	0.9800
C(28)-H(28B)	0.9800
C(28)-H(28C)	0.9800
Cu(1)-O(6)	1.852(3)
Cu(1)-N(2)	1.933(3)
Cu(1)-O(4)	1.974(3)
Cu(1)-O(3)	1.980(3)
Cu(2)-O(2)	1.855(3)
Cu(2)-N(1)	1.934(3)
Cu(2)-O(1)	1.967(3)
Cu(2)-O(5)#1	1.980(3)
O(2)-C(1)-C(14)	116.3(4)
O(2)-C(1)-C(2)	125.6(4)
C(14)-C(1)-C(2)	118.1(4)
C(11)-C(2)-C(1)	117.6(4)
C(11)-C(2)-C(3)	118.5(4)
C(1)-C(2)-C(3)	123.9(4)
N(1)-C(3)-C(2)	121.2(4)
N(1)-C(3)-C(10)	121.0(4)
C(2)-C(3)-C(10)	117.8(3)
N(1)-C(4)-C(5)	106.8(3)
N(1)-C(4)-C(6)	109.9(3)
C(5)-C(4)-C(6)	108.9(3)
N(1)-C(4)-H(4)	110.4
C(5)-C(4)-H(4)	110.4
C(6)-C(4)-H(4)	110.4
O(3)-C(5)-O(1)	123.3(4)
O(3)-C(5)-C(4)	119.0(4)
O(1)-C(5)-C(4)	117.7(3)
C(7)-C(6)-C(4)	115.2(3)
C(7)-C(6)-H(6A)	108.5
C(4)-C(6)-H(6A)	108.5
C(7)-C(6)-H(6B)	108.5
C(4)-C(6)-H(6B)	108.5
H(6A)-C(6)-H(6B)	107.5
C(8)-C(7)-C(9)	110.8(4)

C(8)-C(7)-C(6)	108.7(4)
C(9)-C(7)-C(6)	111.5(4)
C(8)-C(7)-H(7)	108.6
C(9)-C(7)-H(7)	108.6
C(6)-C(7)-H(7)	108.6
C(7)-C(8)-H(8A)	109.5
C(7)-C(8)-H(8B)	109.5
H(8A)-C(8)-H(8B)	109.5
C(7)-C(8)-H(8C)	109.5
H(8A)-C(8)-H(8C)	109.5
H(8B)-C(8)-H(8C)	109.5
C(7)-C(9)-H(9A)	109.5
C(7)-C(9)-H(9B)	109.5
H(9A)-C(9)-H(9B)	109.5
C(7)-C(9)-H(9C)	109.5
H(9A)-C(9)-H(9C)	109.5
H(9B)-C(9)-H(9C)	109.5
C(3)-C(10)-H(10A)	109.5
C(3)-C(10)-H(10B)	109.5
H(10A)-C(10)-H(10B)	109.5
C(3)-C(10)-H(10C)	109.5
H(10A)-C(10)-H(10C)	109.5
H(10B)-C(10)-H(10C)	109.5
C(12)-C(11)-C(2)	121.9(4)
C(12)-C(11)-H(11)	119.1
C(2)-C(11)-H(11)	119.1
C(11)-C(12)-C(13)	121.9(4)
C(11)-C(12)-Cl(1)	119.6(3)
C(13)-C(12)-Cl(1)	118.6(3)
C(14)-C(13)-C(12)	117.9(4)
C(14)-C(13)-H(13)	121.0
C(12)-C(13)-H(13)	121.0
C(13)-C(14)-C(1)	122.7(4)
C(13)-C(14)-H(14)	118.7
C(1)-C(14)-H(14)	118.7
O(5)-C(15)-O(4)	123.5(4)
O(5)-C(15)-C(16)	118.6(4)
O(4)-C(15)-C(16)	117.8(3)
N(2)-C(16)-C(15)	106.7(3)
N(2)-C(16)-C(25)	110.0(3)
C(15)-C(16)-C(25)	108.4(3)
N(2)-C(16)-H(16)	110.5
C(15)-C(16)-H(16)	110.5
C(25)-C(16)-H(16)	110.5
N(2)-C(17)-C(18)	121.4(3)
N(2)-C(17)-C(24)	121.2(3)
C(18)-C(17)-C(24)	117.4(3)
C(23)-C(18)-C(19)	118.0(4)
C(23)-C(18)-C(17)	118.7(4)
C(19)-C(18)-C(17)	123.4(4)
O(6)-C(19)-C(20)	116.2(4)
O(6)-C(19)-C(18)	126.2(4)
C(20)-C(19)-C(18)	117.6(4)

C(21)-C(20)-C(19)	123.0(4)
C(21)-C(20)-H(20)	118.5
C(19)-C(20)-H(20)	118.5
C(20)-C(21)-C(22)	118.1(4)
C(20)-C(21)-H(21)	120.9
C(22)-C(21)-H(21)	120.9
C(23)-C(22)-C(21)	121.5(4)
C(23)-C(22)-Cl(2)	119.4(3)
C(21)-C(22)-Cl(2)	119.1(3)
C(22)-C(23)-C(18)	121.8(4)
C(22)-C(23)-H(23)	119.1
C(18)-C(23)-H(23)	119.1
C(17)-C(24)-H(24A)	109.5
C(17)-C(24)-H(24B)	109.5
H(24A)-C(24)-H(24B)	109.5
C(17)-C(24)-H(24C)	109.5
H(24A)-C(24)-H(24C)	109.5
H(24B)-C(24)-H(24C)	109.5
C(26)-C(25)-C(16)	115.6(3)
C(26)-C(25)-H(25A)	108.4
C(16)-C(25)-H(25A)	108.4
C(26)-C(25)-H(25B)	108.4
C(16)-C(25)-H(25B)	108.4
H(25A)-C(25)-H(25B)	107.4
C(25)-C(26)-C(27)	109.4(4)
C(25)-C(26)-C(28)	110.8(4)
C(27)-C(26)-C(28)	110.8(4)
C(25)-C(26)-H(26)	108.6
C(27)-C(26)-H(26)	108.6
C(28)-C(26)-H(26)	108.6
C(26)-C(27)-H(27A)	109.5
C(26)-C(27)-H(27B)	109.5
H(27A)-C(27)-H(27B)	109.5
C(26)-C(27)-H(27C)	109.5
H(27A)-C(27)-H(27C)	109.5
H(27B)-C(27)-H(27C)	109.5
C(26)-C(28)-H(28A)	109.5
C(26)-C(28)-H(28B)	109.5
H(28A)-C(28)-H(28B)	109.5
C(26)-C(28)-H(28C)	109.5
H(28A)-C(28)-H(28C)	109.5
H(28B)-C(28)-H(28C)	109.5
O(6)-Cu(1)-N(2)	95.59(13)
O(6)-Cu(1)-O(4)	155.81(12)
N(2)-Cu(1)-O(4)	85.08(13)
O(6)-Cu(1)-O(3)	95.51(12)
N(2)-Cu(1)-O(3)	154.56(13)
O(4)-Cu(1)-O(3)	93.92(12)
O(2)-Cu(2)-N(1)	95.71(14)
O(2)-Cu(2)-O(1)	156.32(12)
N(1)-Cu(2)-O(1)	85.07(13)
O(2)-Cu(2)-O(5)#1	94.14(12)
N(1)-Cu(2)-O(5)#1	156.07(13)

O(1)-Cu(2)-O(5)#1	94.47(12)
C(3)-N(1)-C(4)	123.1(3)
C(3)-N(1)-Cu(2)	127.2(3)
C(4)-N(1)-Cu(2)	109.5(3)
C(17)-N(2)-C(16)	123.2(3)
C(17)-N(2)-Cu(1)	127.3(3)
C(16)-N(2)-Cu(1)	109.3(2)
C(5)-O(1)-Cu(2)	112.7(3)
C(1)-O(2)-Cu(2)	125.7(3)
C(5)-O(3)-Cu(1)	113.0(3)
C(15)-O(4)-Cu(1)	112.1(3)
C(15)-O(5)-Cu(2)#2	113.6(3)
C(19)-O(6)-Cu(1)	125.5(3)

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms:

#1 $x-1, y, z$ #2 $x+1, y, z$

Table S6. Anisotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for CuLCl. The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2p^2 [h^2 a^2 U^{11} + \dots + 2 h k a^* b^* U^{12}]$

	U ¹¹	U ²²	U ³³	U ²³	U ¹³	U ¹²
C(1)	11(2)	15(2)	10(2)	-3(2)	2(2)	5(2)
C(2)	10(2)	13(2)	14(2)	-2(2)	-2(2)	3(2)
C(3)	8(2)	14(2)	12(2)	2(2)	-1(2)	2(2)
C(4)	13(2)	9(2)	13(2)	-1(2)	-1(2)	1(2)
C(5)	13(2)	10(2)	15(2)	-2(2)	-2(2)	4(2)
C(6)	15(2)	18(2)	17(2)	2(2)	-4(2)	1(2)
C(7)	22(2)	15(2)	26(2)	3(2)	-3(2)	2(2)
C(8)	41(3)	28(3)	72(4)	21(3)	2(3)	11(3)
C(9)	74(4)	24(3)	40(3)	13(3)	15(3)	3(3)
C(10)	19(2)	14(2)	10(2)	-1(2)	-3(2)	-4(2)
C(11)	12(2)	15(2)	11(2)	1(2)	-1(2)	4(2)
C(12)	11(2)	12(2)	15(2)	-4(2)	-2(2)	2(2)
C(13)	12(2)	7(2)	22(2)	2(2)	-2(2)	2(2)
C(14)	15(2)	13(2)	14(2)	2(2)	3(2)	3(2)
C(15)	14(2)	11(2)	12(2)	-1(2)	1(2)	-5(2)
C(16)	13(2)	9(2)	12(2)	-2(2)	2(2)	-1(2)
C(17)	9(2)	12(2)	11(2)	1(2)	1(2)	-4(2)
C(18)	11(2)	9(2)	13(2)	0(2)	-1(2)	-3(2)
C(19)	11(2)	15(2)	16(2)	2(2)	0(2)	-4(2)
C(20)	18(2)	17(2)	13(2)	3(2)	-4(2)	-3(2)
C(21)	14(2)	12(2)	21(2)	4(2)	-1(2)	0(2)
C(22)	12(2)	11(2)	19(2)	-6(2)	1(2)	-2(2)
C(23)	13(2)	16(2)	11(2)	-1(2)	-1(2)	-3(2)
C(24)	19(2)	14(2)	12(2)	1(2)	4(2)	3(2)
C(25)	14(2)	14(2)	20(2)	0(2)	3(2)	-3(2)
C(26)	21(2)	15(2)	22(2)	0(2)	7(2)	-2(2)
C(27)	39(3)	18(3)	42(3)	2(2)	2(3)	-11(3)
C(28)	47(3)	22(3)	35(3)	14(2)	-11(3)	-4(2)
Cl(1)	23(1)	13(1)	19(1)	-5(1)	-3(1)	-1(1)
Cl(2)	22(1)	15(1)	22(1)	-5(1)	2(1)	3(1)
Cu(1)	15(1)	13(1)	9(1)	-2(1)	-1(1)	-1(1)

Cu(2)	14(1)	12(1)	9(1)	-2(1)	1(1)	0(1)
N(1)	10(2)	10(2)	12(2)	0(1)	1(1)	0(1)
N(2)	13(2)	10(2)	9(2)	-1(1)	1(1)	0(1)
O(1)	17(1)	18(2)	11(1)	-2(1)	0(1)	-1(1)
O(2)	21(1)	15(2)	12(1)	-2(1)	3(1)	-1(1)
O(3)	15(1)	16(2)	14(1)	-2(1)	-1(1)	-3(1)
O(4)	16(1)	17(2)	10(1)	-3(1)	0(1)	-1(1)
O(5)	15(1)	13(2)	13(1)	-1(1)	3(1)	2(1)
O(6)	22(1)	16(2)	8(1)	2(1)	-2(1)	1(1)
